

**UNFORGETTABLE MEMORIES OF CHILDHOOD THE ARTISTIC
ANALYSIS OF THE NOVEL “KITE RUNNER” WRITTEN BY KHALID
HUSAINI**

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Annotation: This novel reflects the childhood of young adolescents in a troubled time in Afghanistan. It focuses mainly on friendship, dignity, valor, loyalty.” Kite runner” the novel was the first work of writer and it was published in more than 40 languages in over 10 million copies. I have done artistic analysis on the form and content of the work.

Key words: exposition, knot, eventful, culmination, unraveling, conclusion.

For a month, I took a book in my hand, and I did not think it would be okay to read it overnight. This work, which I liked and greatly influenced me, is the novel by Khalid Husaini, “Kite Runner”. I found the description of the Uzbek writer Abdulla Kahhor Utkir Hoshimov’s painting “The Desert Air” in this work. This work is pure, warm, natural, warm and pleasant. This novel is a novel about two friends, their fertility in their childhood, their admiration for one another, the kindness that is most compassionate to one another, and the genuine friendliness of our feelings. The main heroes of the work are Amir, Baba, Hasan, Rahimkhon. The ruler is rich, wealthy and wealthy and is the father of Adam, his only son. His friend Hasan is simply a servant, a martyr, a sincere, hardworking son. They have grown up together from youth, play together, but they face many difficulties because of the fate’s unexpected gifts and shots. Although he is a little bit older than Hasan Amir, he does not want to tell it to his friend. In many pictures, Amir has been ignored by Hasan, the Amir knows how to read and write, but he thinks it’s

his job to teach his friend. This novel is often called “Kite Runner”, because these two friends love to fly from heaven to the sky, to participate in barracks. They also run after the wind, just like lampposts, and see their indulgent children as pure. In many leagues, Hasan takes the first place for his friend Amir, who wants the Amir to hear all of them praise. Hasan is a genuine friend, he is even ready to die for the Amir, even though his friend is not worthy of kindness. The ruler is selfish and arrogant, and even slanders his house by accusing Hassan of stealing. But it seems that they are inextricably linked to some kind of friendship. If we analyze this work on the elements of the plot, the exposition of the work starts with the fact that one of the days when Rahimkhan had to see the Baba, and that he had not seen him for a long time would be seen sooner or later, since 1975 . As in every other novel, this novel also has a knot, why this node is such that Amir’s father, Father, is so kind to the son of ordinary servant Hasan, that Amir is just as courageous, courageous, He wants to be a young man, even if he wants his friend Rahimkhon to be like a son of Hasan. This node is removed in the middle of the work. In this context, the development of events is intensely illuminated. That is, they are moving to another city, a special environment, new people, a new place and so on. The culmination of the execution is that Amir’s father died of a serious illness. He no longer has his father, the one who trusted him, and now he has to fight for life, he must eat and should ready for any situation, and there is nobody around him, even his friend. He became isolated, realized that he could not do nothing without the father, and he stepped into a great life. The solution was that Amir had a brother, Rahimkhon called him by letter, and informed him that he had his own brother, that is, his own solution, that is Hasan was his brother that he understood that his younger father was not indifferent to Hasan, the solution to this work. At that time, for some reason he was forced to live separately from his son, and he could tell Rahimkhon Amir of all that he could not beat his son even though he was older. The boy’s contention in the boy’s eyes, while the other children hurt him, Hasan always fought against him.

In conclusion, I would like to say that our true happiness is that true friends have always and always with us, and that there are friends who can help us in bad

times and have good friends. At the same time, they are like our sister and brother, the closest we are. In this game, not only friendship but also humanity, kindness, and emotions are the main reasons for us, I am sure, dear reader, you will read this work as if you were in a day you make the right conclusion. The other works of Khalid Husaini are written in the national language, even though he is a representative of another nation, and all people read his books quickly and easily. Similar to the works of Utkir Hoshimov, Abdulla Kahhor, Odil Yokubov and Said Ahmad, as well as Khalid Hosseini's works.

Used literature

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